

AMURIA BEHAVIORAL STUDY FEEDBACK AND VALIDATION WORKSHOP REPORT

Held on 15th November 2024, at the Peku Hotel, Amuria, Uganda

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About the study

Since 2021 the International Potato Center (CIP) in collaboration with Ministry of Agriculture Animal Husbandry and Fisheries (MAAIF) and the National Agricultural Research Organization (NARO) have been implementing a research designed to test the use of behavioral interventions to stimulate demand for and promote diffusion of improved varieties of sweetpotato in Amuria district. The MAAIF is represented in the study by the District Production Department while NARO is represented by the National Crops Resources Research Institute (NaCRRI) based in Namulonge.

The First phase of this study focused on testing the effect of a bundle of behavioral nudges on demand for quality seed of four improved sweetpotato varieties namely Tanzania, Ejumula, NASPOT 13 and NAROSPOT 1. Under this phase, the study relaxed two key constraints relating to technology adoption namely access/availability and seed quality assurance. This funded SweetGAINS project, an investment by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation on breeding for market-demanded, consumer preferred Root, Tubers and Banana (RTB) crops.

Figure 1: Varieties of sweetpotato used in the study

The second phase of the study tests the effect of two additional behavioral interventions namely i) provision of trial pack of quality seed and ii) cooking and tasting of the improved varieties. The second intervention hence aims at resolving constraints relating to lack of money to purchase and try out a new variety (i.e., liquidity constraint) and the uncertainty about taste (sensory characteristics) of the new variety. Phase two of the study is funded by the CGIAR Initiative on Market Intelligence

(<https://www.cgiar.org/initiative/market-intelligence/>).

It is premised on the understanding that even when the technology is right and market segment targeted by the technology is well defined, there are farmer/household-intrinsic behavioral factors that can impede adoption of improved technologies. The interventions aimed at resolving liquidity constraint and uncertainty of the taste.

Why Amuria?

Amuria district is among the leading producers of sweetpotato in the Teso sub-region of Eastern region in Uganda. Sweetpotato is the second most important food crop after cassava. Several varieties of sweetpotato are grown in the district, most of them farmer varieties. The varieties grown in the district have been in the communities for a long period of time.

Farmers rely on informal seed systems and acquire their seed (also known as vines) from own sources (i.e., recycling), family, neighbors and friends. A small percentage of farmers acquire seed through market purchases, usually from farmers who raise the crop in lowlands areas during dry season with the intention of capturing high offseason prices of roots. Vines are thus sold as a by-product to farmers. The vines from these sources tend to be of poor quality resulting in low yields, with high pest and disease infections.

Amuria had not had any sweetpotato project or program aimed at improving production/productivity, despite the significance of the crop in the district. This project was thus the first to do so.

The roll-out of the Parish Development model – a Uganda government grassroots development initiative – coincided with the launch of this study, making findings of the study serve as baseline conditions on the status of sweetpotato production in Amuria.

2. OPENING SESSION

The Amuria District Agricultural Officer (DAO), Mr. Moses Okim welcomed all the participants to the workshop. He thanked the participants for finding time to attend the workshop and explained that the workshop was a culmination of years of joint implementation of a research project with the International Potato Center and National Agricultural Research Organization. He led the participants through the introductions and the agenda of the workshop.

The DAO then invited the District Town Clerk Mr. Joseph Opio Akol to open the workshop on behalf of the District Chief Administrative Officer (CAO) Ms. Angella Akurut.

Mr. Opio in opening the workshop said that he was delighted to be part of the workshop, and that the CAO could not come because of other pressing engagement but greatly appreciated the research team for choosing to share findings of the research with the District team. He acknowledged the presence of the two Deputy RDCs Ms. Proscovia Arongo and Mr Moses Ibwala and invited them to greet the participants.

Dr. Julius Okello then gave an overview of the project highlighting its main aim was to provide farmers with better quality vines in Amuria district. He communicated that there would be two presentations of findings of the study: quantitative and qualitative

3. SESSION 1: PRESENTATION OF THE FINDINGS OF FARMER SURVEY

The results of farmer survey drawing from the study implemented under the CGIAR Initiative on Market Intelligence was presented by Julius Okello. Key points of the presentation were:

Background

- Sweetpotato is a major food staple in Amuria district
- Amuria district is among the leading sweetpotato produce in Eastern Uganda
- Common products: Amukeke and Inginyo.
- Most popular variety, Osukut, grown over many years.
- Average yields are very low – 4tons/ha versus the optimum of 14tons/ha
- Low yields attributed primarily to accumulation of pests and diseases in the planting material
- Major pest is sweetpotato weevil and white flies while major diseases are sweetpotato virus diseases.

Pests and diseases of sweetpotato

Figure 3: Common pests and disease of sweetpotato in Uganda

Research objectives

- Introduce quality sweetpotato vines free from pests and diseases
- Improve farmers' access to quality vines

Key findings

- 98.5% of farmers grow sweetpotato
- Mostly grown to make food and cash sales
- Most known varieties: Osukut/Tanzania followed by Oboi
- Most planted varieties: Oboi, Osukut, and New Dimbuka (Narospot 1) – implies promoted varieties planted
- Major source of information on sweetpotato seed are: fellow farmers, mass media. Only a few get information from agricultural extensionists

Figure 3: Sources of seeds used by farmers

	Control	Trial pack
Every Season	2%	3%
Every Other Season	9%	10%
Once in a While	42%	44%
Never	48%	43%

	Control	Cooking demo
Every Season	2%	2%
Every Other Season	10%	10%
Once in a While	45%	41%
Never	44%	47%

	Control	Nudge
Every Season	1%	3%
Every Other Season	8%	11%
Once in a While	43%	43%
Never	47%	43%

	Control	Treatment
Every Season	3%	2%
Every Other Season	9%	10%
Once in a While	42%	43%
Never	46%	45%

Table 1: Purchase of seed by treatment type

The presentation concluded by emphasizing the need for profound effort from all stakeholders across the value chain to realize a significant shift in farmers' behavior towards the adoption of improved sweetpotato varieties. The findings highlighted the complexities of changing farming practices and the importance of continued stakeholder engagement and support.

Discussion of the results of household survey

The questions raised by the workshop participants and responses to the question Julius:

Question #1: Thank you Dr. Okello for your statistics, in your research, you have shown that Amuria leads in the production of sweetpotatoes. But, I don't know whether you have taken a step to do your research in other districts in Teso because I believe there is a district that might be leading us, either Ngora or Kumi. Also, it is shocking when you say in your research, because I am down there in the field with some of these farmers, in most cases I don't see a lot of these farmers growing Osukut so much. Surprisingly my sister [i.e., another participant] is confessing that within town council here, people grow it a lot but in the villages, I interface with most farmers and they are so much into Iboi. Thank you. <<Male agricultural officer>>

Response: You are very right, my statistics were showing Teso sub-region as the leading producer of sweetpotato production in Uganda, not Amuria district. On the issue of Iboi being the most grown, this is actually true according to our findings; Osukut was the most heard of variety, but Iboi was the most planted and Osukut came in second.

Question #2: You talked about how locally we produce sweetpotato and make products that you stated, firstly into Amukeke, then the other is dry chips which almost look similar. However, it is not clear how the market linkage works; like after doing this, where does it go in terms of

market? How does a farmer access market for these specific products? Then in terms of processing, what is the objective of the International Potato Centre that puts them in position to incorporate agro processing in terms of modifying it into food that we eat or sell to supermarkets, what you have on that?" <<Male Assistant RDC >>

Response: You have brought up a good topic. There is indeed a plan to setup a sweetpotato processing factory which will be located Serere and will serve the nearby districts Soroti, Ngora, Bukedea, Amuria, and Katakwi. These districts will supply the factory with raw materials. The project is yet to start. We had to first do a study to see what was on ground in terms of farmers' needs and preferences. The project to support farmers in processing, value addition and marketing was supposed to start in 2020 but there have been issues between the World Bank (the funder) and the government which caused the delays. We are hopeful that these issues have been ironed out and the project will commence soon.

Question #3: Now, I'm wondering, when I connect it to the issue of sustainability, (some of) the new varieties easily rots when it takes long in the garden and yet our old variety takes longer and it doesn't rot except for the pests and diseases that sometimes affect it. Have you come up with a more convenient strategy to ensure that the new variety will be able to give bigger quantities instead of rotting in the garden? Because when you look at a variety like Iboi and other old varieties, here and in Katakwi, we are interested in storage for purposes of food and yet in Ngora, Kumi and Bukedea they have gone commercial. For them they have a variety of sweetpotatoes, the Tanzanian one, in fact when you go to Kampala and say 'yellow yellow!', they rush for it. For it when harvest starts, you can get a lot of money [due to high price], but as time goes on, the price dips. You can sell a bag at about 100,000shs, but after one or two months, when many other people are harvesting, you sell the same bag at around 15,000shs. That discourages the farmer. Is there a way you plan to address this issue? My last one [question] is about the issue of having sweetpotato transformed into different products. You know Amukeke is one of the ways we preserve sweetpotatoes. I remember even when we were in school we would carry it in our bags and that smell alone would make others ask us about it, they were interested in knowing what kind of sweetpotato that was. For us, we know that in English it is 'amukeks'. It is actually a name which we dubbed and was adopted, now people really think it is called 'Amukeks'. So, do you have a name for it, so that we also sustain our way of storing our sweetpotatoes, even this one that is pounded for flour? So, we are now looking at getting many products and also getting market from outside, like exporting it. I think maybe my argument is driving towards

marketability, sustainability and storage. Thank you. <<Male Town clerk>>

Response: You bring up a good point. I have actually noted down that name ‘Amukeks’, it’s the first time I’m hearing about it. I think there is a company in the north called “Divine Organic Foods” that is selling products from sweetpotato so it is possible to produce many products from sweetpotato. It is also true that the current varieties are softer than Osukut and they are orange fleshed in colour. They are meant to solve the problem of food and nutrition security especially vitamin A deficiency.

SESSION 2. PRESENTATION OF RESULTS OF QUALITATIVE RESEARCH

Dr. Irene Bayiyana presented the findings of the qualitative study which encompassed focus group discussions (FGDs), semi-structured interviews (SSIs) and key informant interviews (KIIs). The presentation focused on the status of sweetpotato production, variety preference, use and vine sources. The key points of the presentation are summarized:

Background:

- Qualitative study implemented in a sub sample of the overall study
- Focused on only the new varieties that were introduced by the project

Methods:

- The study comprised 12 FGDs, 10 SSIs and 21 KIIs
- FGDs were conducted in 6 treatment villages (2 who received trial packs, 2 who received consumption interventions only and 2 that received both trial packs and consumption interventions. There were, on average, eight farmers per FGD.

Key findings

- Osukut is the most preferred variety mainly because of its sweet taste, followed by being liked by animals, sweet and quality products, short cooking time and liked by children.
- Vine loss due to drought was the main reason for abandoning some of the new varieties.
- Main sources of planting material were own garden and neighbors for both men and women.
- More women purchased vines from salespersons while more men purchased vines from the market.
- The main reasons for low vine purchase especially among women were financial/liquidity constraints and vine purchase being perceived as a man’s role.
- Financial/liquidity constraints, vine loss due to drought, inadequate land, and pests and diseases were the main challenges to adoption of new varieties.

- Trial packs enabled farmers to select varieties based on preferences, increased demand and motivated farmers to plant new varieties.
- Cooking/consumption intervention increased demand for quality vines of sweetpotato
- Ability to select variety based on taste preferences also increased with consumption intervention

Figure xx. Effects of trial packs (%)

Figure xx: Effects of cooking intervention

Discussion of the findings of qualitative study

Below is a summary of the discussions around the results of the qualitative study:

Question #1: “You presented the issue of land being small but I would like to know, did you do a survey on the type of soil? Because you might find that some places have sandy soils, but that is not the case for the whole of Teso, different sub counties have different types of soil. Maybe this could inform the reasons why some varieties are not accepted.” <<Male female Deputy RDC>>

Response: We did not do this because it was not within the scope of our study.

Okello’s response: Maybe to add on that, in our quantitative study, we asked the respondents whether they thought their soils were fertile or not. But the problem with that is that it is just a perspective and it’s not very reliable. Testing the soils can give better picture of nature of soils. However, soil testing surveys are very expensive to carry out.

DAO’s response: We did soil testing in some of the sub counties, but up to now we have not gotten feedback and when we ask, they say it’s a huge exercise and they have to

take the samples to Nairobi for analysis and that we should be patient until we get the results.

Agricultural Officer's response: I think I can also support this [that the soil testing is expensive]. I got a chance when I was working with some NGO back then to do trials and test for soil nutrients. It is a very expensive investment that requires a lot of reagents, especially when testing for phosphorus, nitrogen and potassium. We were in Namulonge for almost one month to train on how to do soil testing. Most of the agriculturalists may not know how little of it [soil testing] we learnt in school. It requires a lot of practical work. Moreover, it requires [expensive] reagents and the only source of those reagents is Makerere University. Otherwise, you have to get from outside the country [import]. Then the soil testing kit itself is also very expensive, Thank you.

Question #2: How did you measure the yields of various varieties of sweetpotato to know which variety is doing better than the other? <<Sub county chief>>

Response: The yield was defined as the number of edible and marketable roots produced from the variety. By edible we mean those that are free from disease. However, actual yield may be difficult to determine because of piecemeal harvesting.

Okello's response: Estimating yield in sweetpotato has always been very challenging. Farmers typically harvest sweetpotato piecemeal, as needed. A little today to eat, a little the other day to sell and buy basic small household goods like salt and sugar. Hence self-reported yield estimates can be very unreliable, but that is what we often depend on.

Agricultural Officer: It is true that our farmers harvest continuously throughout the season in small amounts each time. In other districts, such as Ngora, sweetpotato is grown for business and their farmers tend to harvest all in one go. That makes it easy to estimate yields.

4. SESSION 3: BREAKOUT SESSIONS

To provide feedback on the results and assess changes in behavior (outcomes) due to the implemented interventions, the participants were divided into three breakout groups based on expertise as:

1. Farmers
2. Technical (i.e., agricultural officers)
3. Policy (district decisionmakers)

Each group was asked to discuss and report to following set of questions:

1. Preliminary results show that at the beginning of the season people usually don't have money to buy seed/vines. How do we solve that problem?
2. How can we make seed/vines of new varieties more available in the market?
3. How can we ensure timely seed delivery/ distribution of new varieties?
4. How do we ensure that farmers can find quality seed/vines?
5. Which of these things you have recommended have you done?

BREAKOUT GROUP 1: FARMERS

Response to Question #1

- Make agricultural loans accessible by lowering the interest rates. *"We are lucky now that PDM is around, that most people have benefited. I myself benefited, those vines are normally sold at 25,000shs per sack and when I get one million, I think I'm able to afford it."* Male farmer.
- Increase accessibility and reliability of the market for agricultural products. It is a big challenge because the market is not reliable.
- Creating a saving culture among farmers to ensure that we can afford vines when the season starts.
- Formation of cooperatives to bargain better and to share information.
- Input financing for farmers in groups. *"They can bring vines to a model farmer to multiply and make them available to other farmers. It will ensure that there are no excuse of having not planted in time because of no seed."* Female farmer.
- Government should subsidize the planting materials for farmers. *"Some people cannot afford the vines where I come from and if the price can be reduced to like 15,000shs or even count the number of vines and sell maybe 10 at 500shs, I think it will be fairer such that everyone can afford it."* Male farmer.

Responses to Question #2

- Providing improved planting materials at fair price to farmers; so that everyone can afford them.
- Ensure timely delivery of vines to farmers. One male farmer said: *"They come sometimes when the rain has not even started or when people have already finished heaping and have even/[already] used old varieties."*
- Increasing the number of salespersons in the villages, *"Like where I come from there is only one."* Male farmer.
- Educate farmers (extension education). There is need for more extension workers as one female farmer mentioned, *"It is true because they are overwhelmed with work. The ratio of extension worker to farmer is 1 to 2000 which is not achievable and yet the standard ratio is 1 extension worker to 500 households."*

- Provide farmers with samples of new varieties (roots for boiling and vines). *“They normally bring only the vines. I think they can also bring the roots so that we can taste.”* Male farmer.
- Contract farming of the new varieties (vine multipliers). One female farmer said, *“We have to get more vine multipliers within the localities, not from outside/far; but we can train some farmers on how to multiply vines.”*

Responses to Question #3

- Have vine multipliers within the villages or sub county.
- Link the farmer, salesperson and the researcher to ensure faster delivery of information.
- Improve access roads for easy delivery of vines.
- Decentralize multiplication centres i.e. at district or subcounty level. *“Instead of having to go to Namulonge/Serere, why can't we decentralize at district level or even subcounty level where I can ride my bicycle to pick the vines.”* Male farmer.
- Invest in more vehicles to deliver and distribute vines on time. *“They only use one vehicle which makes us wait for long and distribution is so slow.”*

Responses to Question #4

- Proper/timely extension education about improved varieties. *“In Obalanga subcounty, extension workers have established what they call plant clinics where farmers are educated on identifying the seeds which are of poor quality. So, it is good if these plant clinics are established in most of the sub counties.”* Male farmer.
- Collaboration with research stations like Serere and Namulonge with farmers.
- Intervention of policy makers to protect farmers from buying poor quality varieties. One male farmer submitted, *“Here in my place, somebody can plant NAROCASS 1 in their cassava garden but its tubers are diseased and yet he still sells to the farmers. So, we really need the policymakers to come in and make laws that if you are found selling the diseased seeds, there is a law that will attack you.”* But concern was raised about such policy. One participant stated: *“My worry is that in case a policy is put in place stating that only improved seed should be sold, what will happen to those farmers who are unable to buy? Are they not going to be put off production? In case of such a policy, how do we protect those farmers who cannot afford improved vines?”* Male farmer.
- Buying seeds from reliable sources like research stations.

Responses to Q #5

- We have bought improved vines.
- We have sought extension services.
- Being in farmer groups or saving groups.

Additional feedback

“When you give us these vines, you don't follow up like maybe sometimes you plant and get poor yields and nobody comes to explain why the yields were poor. Also, the issue of proper handling of vines, I remember there is a year when they brought vines and they got rotten in the sacks because we already had the local ones and we really made a loss.” Male farmer.

“In our salespoints we sell to farmers but some farmers come back complaining to us that some of the varieties don't yield well. So, we have not been given the provision to report farmers' feedback. We really need a platform where we can give feedback on what is happening and what farmers are saying. There should be a place where we can submit such complaints because instead, they blame us when the variety is not doing well.” Female salesperson.

BREAKOUT GROUP 2: TECHNICAL TEAM

Response to Question #1

- Vine preservation by heaping sweetpotatoes in the lowland or swampy areas or within the banana plantation so that they can have shade. Or you can plant sweetpotatoes under big trees to preserve the vines.
- Producer cooperatives/VSLAs/money lenders to provide vines on credit to the farmers who can recover after harvest.
- Establishing contract agreements with farmers e.g., CIP can give vines on credit which allow farmers to pay later.
- Accessing agricultural loans from the financial institutions like post bank, opportunity bank, etc.

Responses to Question #2

- Linking farmers to local seed business groups which multiply improved seeds.
- Increase the number of salespersons to make vines locally available and accessible to farmers.
- Establishment of demonstration farms so that farmers can learn sweetpotato production practices.
- Participation of extension workers in provision of information about new varieties.
- Subsidizing prices of vines of new varieties so that the whole community can afford them.
- [Create] public awareness of the availability of improved varieties, for example, through different media such as radio or social media.

Response to Question #3

- By creating structures from the district to farmer level.
- Timely delivery of weather forecast information that informs the farmer of when to access and buy the new varieties to avoid making losses. Vines should be delivered at the onset of rains.

- Creation of farmer groups to enable bulk vines. *“In this area, when people are brought together in a group, they ... have the voice to advocate for inputs in bulk that can support their production activities.”* Male Agricultural officer.

- “Formation of local certified seed business groups at village level that multiply quality seeds and ease access of seeds to farmers.” Male Agricultural officer.

Response to Question #4

- Through awareness creation on new technologies.
- Establishment of demonstration sites at the level of model farmers so that other farmers are able to learn from there.
- Creation of sales agents at village level to ensure that farmers get the vines.
- Inspection by agricultural officers to ensure quality of the vines is not compromised.
- Establishment of vine multiplication sites in every sub county. This way, farmers can access the vines on time when they are still fresh.
- Research linkage: link the farmers to the producers of the vines such as NARO.

Response to Question #5

- Awareness creation.
- Demo setups. *“We established the sweetpotato sites.”* Male Agricultural officer.
- Formation of local seed groups though not done in all sub counties.
- Inspection. *“We visit farmers and give guidance and also listen to farmers’ challenges and give recommendations”*.
- Dissemination of weather forecasts so that farmers know when to begin production.
- Linkage of farmers to research institutes so that they can access inputs.
- Capacity building (extension education) for the farmers on new technologies of farming.

Discussion

Question: “I just wanted clarification on LSBs.” Female farmer.

Response: “These are local seed business groups that are established at the district level. It’s not a common approach here but in other regions it is playing a very big role in increasing access to seeds. These local seed business groups are people who are trained on all the basic agronomy of producing quality seed. So, instead of having

only a few that can plant and give us seed, these groups are supposed to be our multipliers. When they multiply, we inspect and certify their seeds so that you can purchase from them instead of going to Serere.” Male Agricultural officer.

Question: “According to what you have already done, you have established a model farm, a site where people learn from. Can you tell us exactly where this site is.” Assistant RDC.

Response: “I know of farmers that have been multiplying those new varieties of seed like Narospot 1 and Naspot 13. Like in Obalanga I have about four farmers doing this.” Male Agricultural officer.

BREAKOUT GROUP 3: POLICYMAKERS

Responses to Question #1

- Integrate the component of saving for seed within already existing village savings and loans associations (VSLAs).
- Train local farmers within the community to become vine multipliers (capacity building). *“We could also put it as a policy that each subcounty or perhaps a district has what we call vine multipliers. Having vine multipliers within the community can help farmers who don’t have money to get vines on credit which can be repaid later on which is harder to do when the vine multiplier is from another district or subcounty as they may not easily trust the farmer.”* DAO.
- Policies which encourage diversification: encourage farmers to diversify their income sources at household level.
- Mindset change is very key: need to continuously educate people on the different ways they can earn a decent living whereby they can afford to buy improved varieties.

Response to Question #2

- Establish and support local farmers to become multipliers of improved varieties. In that way they can easily supply to the market.
- Increase vine selling points in the communities.
- Increase the collaborative aspect with research institutes to ensure constant supply of new varieties in the communities which would increase availability in the market.
- Need to continuously promote policies that encourage awareness creation of availability of the new varieties. The varieties may be there but they won’t be taken up if the farmers are not given this information. Many people do not know that orange fleshed sweetpotatoes are rich in vitamin A and if you tell them Vitamin A, they may not know the relevance of vitamin A until you tell them. So, once you create awareness on such things, then they will become more in the market.”

Response to Question #3

- Establish more sales points in the community. The DAO said, “*Time deals with nearness and availability.*” The more the sale points, the easier access at the right time becomes.
- Training more vine multipliers among local farmers to increase access points which makes timely delivery possible.
- Monitoring/follow up of the trained vine multipliers to ensure timely production/multiplication.
- Engaging/building capacity of technical staff/extension workers to support the vine multipliers to ensure timely vine production which in turn allows time delivery to farmers.
- Improve roads to improve timely transportation of vines.

Response to Question #4

- Strengthen systems of pests and disease surveillance to ensure quality vines for farmers.
- Promote coordination and collaboration with research institutes to ensure availability of quality vines.
- Build the knowledge capacity of the farmers, vine multipliers and extension staff on the aspect of using quality seed and being able to identify quality vines.
- Close inspection and supervision of multiplication sites to ensure varieties are not mixed up to maintain quality.

Response to Question #5

- Surveillance and reporting of pests and diseases by extension staff.
- Strengthen the collaboration between farmers, extension and research. “*This is happening right now as we have farmers, extension workers and researchers in the same workshop deliberating on the issues that improve sweetpotato production.*” DAO.
- We also engage stakeholders on the availability of new varieties and bring awareness to the community.
- Strengthen quality control policies by supporting inspection.

CLOSING CEREMONIES

Closing remarks from Dr. Julius Okello

Dr. Julius Okello thanked all participants for their active engagement in the group breakout and general discussions. He thanked the research team for their commitment to implementing the study. He then thanked the DAO and other officials for being closely involved in the entire study. He thanked all the salespersons for their diligence in reaching the farmers and thanked the farmers for being willing to learn. He concluded by thanking all the participants for taking time to participate in the workshop for actively contributing to the discussions

Closing remarks from the DAO

The DAO – Mr. Moses Okim – thanked all participants of the workshop and the NARO team for supporting his research to gain more knowledge.

Closing remarks from office of the CAO

The Town clerk, representing the office of District CAO thanked all participants for their involvement and admonished them to hold fast to all recommendations that were made throughout the workshop. He then thanked the DAO for the smooth coordination. He urged the farmers to pass on the information and knowledge obtained from the workshop to their fellow farmers. He also thanked the NARO and CIP team for identifying Amuria as a beneficiary district of the study.

Closing remarks from office of the RDC

The two deputy RDCs both expressed their joy at being part of the workshop as it was their first time attending such an engagement since their posting in the district. The Deputy RDC, Ms. Proscovia, thanked all participants for being part of the workshop. She then thanked the partners for the collaboration and good relationship created with the district. She then went on to confirm the study findings on Osukut’s popularity and preference among the farmers. She noted that: “there is a certain nostalgia or attachment to the Osukut variety which has developed resistance among the people to take on new varieties. It is very common for school-going children here to take sweetpotato to school as it is a big part of our diet.” She further affirmed the importance of sweetpotato in Amuria district and highlighted a knowledge gap among stakeholders of the new varieties. She especially indicated that most stakeholders are not aware, have no knowledge of, and cannot differentiate between the new varieties and therefore recommended creation of more awareness. She further asked for the strengthening protection of farmers from being cheated with fake vines. She acknowledged the participants’ efforts in generating insightful and innovative ideas on addressing challenges in the potato industry to improve production. She finally thanked NARO and CIP for the expertise invested in training farmers to grow better varieties for development.

Awarding of certificates to best performing salespersons

The Deputy RDCs and Town Clerk officiated the presentation of certificates and financial awards to six best performing salespersons. Performance was based on volume of vine sales they sold to farmers. The recipients of the awards and certificates were

1. John Robert Otim – Abakuli village
2. Rose Asaete – School Cell
3. Hellen Aligoi – Aroro village
4. Johnson Osege – Central Cell
5. Christine Alupo Okello – Agerger village
6. Augustine Oraida – Ooloi village

Closing of workshop

The Deputy RDC officially closed the workshop.

Lunch and group photo

During the lunch meal, one female salesperson expressed her gratitude towards the research team and stated, *“We as salespersons want to start an association of sweetpotato vine sellers called CIP family, I hope you people can guide us on this.”*

An official at the district (The District Land Surveyor) also shared his experience with one of the new varieties as elaborated in the following quotation, *“I got to know about the vines from the project and went to buy from a vine multiplier in Bukedea and I gave them to my father to plant. My father planted an acre and got three bags and some of the roots were round and small, others were thin like strings while others were very big and cracked. Disappointed, my father told me to take back my varieties, and let him continue with his old ones, and I laughed hysterically.”* The official bought the varieties but did not master their names and so could not tell which variety had turned out as described.

Appendices

Appendix 1: List of workshop participants

#	Name	Designation	Email	Sex
Research & support Team				
1	Sam Namanda	Agronomist -Associate Scientist	S.Namanda@cgiar.org	M
2	Julius Okello	Impact Assessment		
3	Irene Bayiyana	Agricultural Economist - Consultant	irene_bayi@yahoo.com	F
4	Harriet Ayoko	Research Assistant	harrietayoko@gmail.com	F
5	Daisy Kemigisha	Rapporteur	Daisykemie@gmail.com	F
6	Jacob	Driver		
7	John Otukei	Research Assistant		
Farmers				
1	xx	Farmer,		
2	Amao Anna Rose	Farmer, School-cell village, Akisim Parish, Amuria Town Council		F
3	Otwao Emmanuel	Farmer, Okepia Village, Arapai Parish, Kuju Subcounty		M
4	Asio Christine	Farmer, Odoon Center Village, Apeduru Parish, Apeduru sub-county		F
5	Onyait Wilbroda	Farmer & vine salesperson, Amuso Village, Ajokomot Parish, Amolo sub-county		M
6	Amuso Florence	Farmer, Market Village, Orungo Town Board Parish, Orungo Subcounty		F
District Team				
1	Moses Okim	DAO Amuria		M
2	Angella Akutut	CAO Amuria	akepudu@gmail.com	F
3	Ejolu Nathan	SAO, Abarilela subcounty, Amuria	nejolu@yahoo.com	M
4	Dennis Odeke	SAO, Kuju subcounty, Amuria	odekedennis2@gmail.com	M
5	Justin Orena	SAO, Morungatuny & Olwa subcounties, Amuria	just.orena84@gmail.com	M
6	Alfred Opok	Senior Entomologist Amuria	alfopoka@gmail.com	M
7	Emmanuel Akelem	District Planner- Amuria	emmakelem@gmail.com	M
8	xxxx	RDC		
9	James Eaku	SAO, Wila sub-county		
10	xxx	SAO, Akeriau sub-county		
11	xxx	SAO, Asamuk sub-county		
12	Mr. Odongo	SAO Wera		
13	Mr. Odokonyero	District Fisheries		
Salespersons (top performers) for awards				
1	John Robert Otim			
2	Rose Asaete			
3	Hellen Aligoi			
4	Johnson Osege			
5	Christine Alupo Okello			
6	Agustine Oraida			

Appendix 2: Workshop Program

TIME	ACTIVITY	RESPONSIBLE
9.00-9.30	Registration	Harriet Ayoko/John Otukey
9.30-9.45	Welcome and introductions	Moses Okim
9.45-10.00	Introduction to the workshop agenda	Julius Okello
10.00-10.30	Sweetpotato production – status, variety preference, use, vine sources: Household survey findings	Julius Okello
10.30-11.30	TEA BREAK	
11.30-12.00	Sweetpotato production – status, variety preference, use, vine sources: Focus group & informant interviews	Irene Bayiyana
12.00-13.00	Breakout groups (Farmers; Technical; Policy)	Irene Bayiyana
13.00-13.30	Closing: remarks by RDC, CAO & Awards	Moses Okim
13.30-14.30	LUNCH BREAK	